

VOCATIONAL GUIDANCE OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS BASED ON THE CLUSTER APPROACH

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Annotation

This article will talk about the newly introduced “cluster” in the field of education, “cluster of pedagogical education”, its meaning, practical significance in pedagogy. Also, the principles, theoretical and pedagogical aspects of the professional development of future physical education teachers are scientifically based.

Keywords: cluster, pedagogical education cluster, physical education, professional development, methodological training.

Introduction.

About the meaning of the word “cluster”, in which the bot is currently used, first of all, we need to find out. The English word is “cluster”, which means such meanings as “tarmoq”, “shingil”, “to‘plam”. This term is a new word that has not yet been included in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language. The term “cluster” is very young. He was brought into the field of economics by Michael Porter in the 1990s. And it is now entering the field of Education. At the end of 2011, a large project was launched, carried out by the customer of the Ministry of Education, dedicated to the study of the necessary conditions for the development of educational clusters and the formation of fixed assets. By education cluster <http://clusters.ntf.ru/sayt> also currently operating.

The cluster of pedagogical education is the consistent cooperation of specialist persons and institutions in order to achieve the expected effect in the process of education and training. Therefore, the cluster of innovative pedagogical education as the main scientific topic of the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of the Tashkent region was established by the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 14, 2021 No. 213. The cluster of pedagogical education plays an important role in the practical formation of the professional skills of future teachers, since the main attention in this process is paid to the formation of practical skills. Among the types of education, the lack of personnel worthy of pedagogical activity, the lack

of in-depth study of the requirements and proposals for training are evidence of the relevance of the study.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. Professional requirements for future teachers, the teacher was expressed in the works of Eastern thinkers Ismail al-Bukhari, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhon Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abdurakhman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Jalaliddin Davoni, Abdullah Avlani. The problems of training teachers in higher educational institutions are covered by a number of literature by our republic and foreign specialists. Issues of formation of the personality of the future teacher in the process of higher education, increasing the social activity of students on the basis of self-government and diagnosing professional formation M.A.Abdullajanova, A.A.Abdulina, A.A.Akbarov, X.A.Abdurakhmanova, S.V.Studied in the studies of safonovas. Pedagogical scientists who studied the professional skills of the teacher H.Abdukarimov, N.Azizkhojayeva, A.Alijev, Yu.A.Akhrorov, A.A.Verbitsky, R.H.Jo 'reyev, B.R.Jo' rayeva, J.G'. Yuldashev, S.M.Markova, G.M.Makhmutova, L.M.Mitina, A.G.Morazov, O.N.Nishanaliyev, M.Ochilov, B.Rakhimov, N.Saidahmedov, V.A.Slastyanin, A'.Talipov, A.R.Khadjabayev, A.A.Khaligav, N.Shadiyev, A.Hyderrova, A.A.Hamidov, F.R.In the work of the yuzlikayev, the pedagogical skills of future teachers, the possibilities of using educational technologies, the worldview of students, Ways and methods of developing a professional and communication culture, as well as, the problems of professional education and training were investigated.In addition to these, the cluster of pedagogical education, professional pedagogy, preparation for professional activities are professors and teachers of TVChDPI: G'.Mohammedov, D.Himmataliyev, F.Zhumanova, A.Zhaborova, S.Tashtemirova, Sh.Batarova, J.Usarav, O Khadjamqulav, J.Yuldashev, F.It was also studied by scientists such as Ochilov.

Future physical education teachers form an interest in learning news about their profession, achievements in science and technology. This, in turn, leads to the formation of skills for independent education, self-development. Together with this, it forms skills to gain prestige in the teaching team. Also, when we increase the need for success in students, the necessary professional skills are formed, such as competitiveness, work on oneself.

Conclusions.The needs of society for qualified and high-quality personnel are determined by the development of Science and practice, increasing requirements for the development of the human personality, the ability to quickly and adequately respond to changing social processes and situations, the willingness to rebuild their activities and the willingness to skillfully solve new,

more complex problems. Self-development, independent work on oneself is the mastery of professional skills.

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